

Prevalence of *Enterobius vermicularis* Infection Among School-Aged Children in Babylon Province

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ABSTRACT:

Background: *Pinworm* or *threadworm* is another name for *Enterobius vermicularis*, is one of the most common intestinal nematodes worldwide and infects around a billion individuals regardless of socioeconomic status, especially children.

Aims: The current investigation was conducted to investigate the frequency and therapeutic implications of *Enterobius vermicularis* infection among school-age children in Babylon Governorate, Iraq using conventional PCR targeting two diagnostic markers (18S rRNA and COX1 genes).

Methodology: Out of 80 clinical samples, a total of identification those isolates was found to be confirmed *Enterobius vermicularis* (37.5%). From 800 children aged 2–10 years (12 male and 18 female) who attended Al-Imam Neighborhood Health Centre for Healthcare, Babylon from May 2025 to July 2025 specimens were collected using Scotch-tape method: fecal specimen and adhesive tape from the perianal region. Molecular detection using PCR with primers against 18S rRNA and COX1 genes was conducted to confirm the species and detect *E. vermicularis* accurately.

Results: In a recent study, 30 out of 80 samples (37.5%) were identified as *Enterobius vermicularis* using the Scotch tape method and Direct faecal wet mount method (DFWM). The infection was most common among children aged 2–5 years, followed by 6–8 years, and least common in those aged 9–10 years. The prevalence was marginally higher in females (18/30) than in males (12/30). Molecular detection by PCR

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showed that the 18S rRNA gene was detected in all 30 positive samples (100%), while the COX1 gene was detected in 26 samples (86%).

Conclusion: The study indicates that *Enterobius vermicularis* infection is relatively common among school-aged children, particularly those aged 2–5 years, with a slightly higher prevalence in females. Molecular analysis confirmed the reliability of 18S rRNA PCR for detecting all positive cases, while COX1 PCR showed slightly lower sensitivity, highlighting the importance of using multiple genetic markers for accurate diagnosis and epidemiological surveillance.

Keywords: 18S rRNA , COX1 gene , PCR, *Enterobius vermicularis*.

INTRODUCTION:

A common parasitic infection affecting mainly children, *Enterobius vermicularis* is an intestinal nematode responsible for enterobiasis (1). Confrontist diagnosis depends on microscopic examination of characteristic eggs using the Scotch-tape method. Nearly 200 million individuals worldwide suffer with *Enterobius vermicularis*, often referred to as pinworm or *Oxyuris vermicularis* (2). A pinworm infestation (*Enterobius vermicularis*). The embryonated eggs hatch in the small intestine after consumption, releasing the larvae. The adult pinworms mainly attach themselves in the caecum and the appendix (3). Re-infection occurs easily in enterobiasis, and the prevalence of this infection mainly depends on public health and personal hygiene (4). About 40% of cases of enterobiasis are asymptomatic, and most instances of pinworm infection are harmless (5). Symptoms include perianal pruritus, insomnia, restlessness, and irritability. In the case of appendicitis, appendiceal colic is a distinctive symptom (6)

This intestinal infection, called enterobiasis, is a major global public health concern. Vulvovaginitis, ileocolitis, mesenteric abscess, salpingitis, appendicitis, or no symptoms at all are possible manifestations. Perianal itching, sleeplessness, restlessness, appetite loss, weight loss, irritability, stomach discomfort, and nausea are some of the symptoms. Even though *E. vermicularis* has been the focus of several investigations, little is known

about its geographic range. Given the lack of attention given to the spread of Enterobiasis in Iraq, even a basic geographical mapping of cases that have been documented might be helpful. Perianal folliculitis, anal dermatitis, and ischio-rectal abscess are other possible indirect signs ⁷. Scratching may lead to autoinfection or transmission because it produces eggs that can readily adhere to fingers or beneath fingernails and spread ⁸. Rarely, vulvovaginitis—an irritation or inflammation of the area—may be indirectly caused by pinworms ⁹. Due to the female worm's nocturnal egg-laying activity on the perianal skin, the adhesive tape test, also called the Scotch tape test, is thought to be the most efficient approach for making a definite diagnosis of *E. vermicularis* (10) Two important molecular markers for identifying *Enterobius vermicularis* are the COX1 gene and 18S rRNA. Both markers are beneficial for precise identification and epidemiological research; the COX1 gene is helpful for genetic analysis and species confirmation, while the 18S rRNA gene offers very sensitive diagnostic detection ¹¹. In endemic areas, combining traditional and molecular methods strengthens public health strategies and helps monitor infection trends among youngsters and other high-risk populations. The purpose of the research is to look at the clinical consequences and *Enterobius vermicularis* infection frequency in school-age children

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Sample Preparation and Study Design

The current research examines the prevalence of *Enterobius vermicularis* in children using a cross-sectional approach. All children provided faecal samples and Scotch-tape samples for specimen collection. All specimens were handled following proper biosafety protocols to ensure the integrity of the samples. This study design allowed for a comprehensive assessment of *E. vermicularis* prevalence within the target population while maintaining methodological rigour.

Ethical Consideration

Every youngster (participant) gave their required oral informed consent. To guarantee that no children were put in danger or harmed during sample collection, all laboratory operations adhered to established guidelines.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The research included children between the ages of two and ten who could provide faecal or Scotch-tape samples. Students who did not provide the necessary permission or who were using anthelmintic or antiprotozoal drugs at the sample time or in the month before were not included.

Gathering, Transporting, and Preserving Faecal Samples

There was a 20 mL sterile screw-capped bottle and a wooden applicator available to participants in order to collect faecal samples. Using the supplied applicator, participants were instructed to gather about five grams of faeces. Additionally, they apparently received explicit instructions not to come into touch with blood, urine, or other unpleasant materials. The vials were sent to the Parasitology Laboratory after being tightly sealed. When the material was received in the vials, 2.5% potassium dichromate solution (K₂Cr₂O₇) weight/volume was employed as a preservation

medium. It was then refrigerated at 4°C until it was examined under a light microscope.

Identification of parasites, microscopic analysis, and laboratory processing

This includes visually analyzing samples using a Scotch-tape procedure and two mixed methods on fecal samples, incorporating formal ether sedimentation (FES) and the direct faecal wet mount technique (DFWM).

Examining Scotch-Tape Samples

In the Scotch-tape method, the perianal region's surface was gently covered with adhesive tape, which was then put on a marked glass slide for microscopic study. in a light microscope, (WESWOX OPTIK; Model: BXLI) while scanning fields from low magnification (10×) to higher one (40×) for better clarity and resolution

Fecal Sample Examination

Seven fecal samples were collected with sterile containers and parasite data was obtained according to standard parasitological methods through the detection of eggs or adult forms of *E. vermicularis*. Lower the chance of overlooking positive samples. DFWM and FES were used in the laboratory to process faecal samples. For the DFWM procedures, a single drop of a homogenised mixture of one gram of faeces and one millilitre of normal saline (0.9% w/v) was analysed on a glass slide using an iodine stain. Similarly, 2 g of faeces and 10 mL of normal saline were combined in a 15 mL conical centrifuge tube for FES, well mixed, and filtered through a tea strainer. The material was then centrifuged for three minutes at a speed of 2000 revolutions per minute. (12) Following the removal of the supernatant, the tube was filled with 10 mL of 10% formalin and 4 mL of ether. The mixture was then centrifuged once more at 2000 rpm for three minutes (13). In order to look for potential parasite eggs and cysts, a single drop of the sediment was placed onto a glass slide with iodine stain and

examined under a microscope at 10x magnification, then confirmed at 40x magnification after all the supernatant layers had been discarded.

Identification of *E. vermicularis*

Parasite identification of *E. vermicularis* eggs was performed exclusively based on egg morphology, following established diagnostic criteria. Ova were identified using standard morphological features, such as colour (colourless and unstained), opacity (translucent), form (planoconvex, with one side convex and the other flattening), eggshell properties (hyaline, thin, smooth, transparent), egg content (carrying a fully grown larva), and approximate size ($50\text{--}60 \times 20\text{--}30 \mu\text{m}$), even though oculomicrometry was not performed. Higher-resolution objective lenses were used to improve microscopic views, and mobile cameras were used to take pictures for documentation (Figure 1).

DNA Extraction from *Enterobius vermicularis*

As directed by the DNA extraction kit's manufacturer, genomic DNA was extracted from perianal samples obtained using the adhesive tape (Scotch tape) technique. extracted using a commercial kit based on a silica column from adult worms or samples containing eggs. After being lysed in lysis buffer containing Proteinase K, the

samples were incubated at 56°C until they were fully digested. To increase the production of DNA from egg samples, mechanical disruption was used to shatter the thick shell. Following lysis, the liquid was sent to a spin column for DNA binding after ethanol was added. DNA was eluted in nuclease-free water after the column was cleaned twice to get rid of impurities. Before being examined further, the isolated DNA was kept at -20°C .

Molecular Detection of *Enterobius vermicularis*

The 18S rRNA gene was the focus of a traditional polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the molecular identification of *Enterobius vermicularis* (Table 1). 5 μL of template DNA, 1 μL of each primer (10 pmol/ μL), 12.5 μL of 2 \times PCR Master Mix, and nuclease-free water made up the total reaction volume of 25 μL used for amplification. The cycling conditions employed for PCR amplification were initial denaturation at 95°C for 5 minutes, 35 cycles of denaturation at 95°C for 30 seconds, annealing at 56°C for 30 seconds, extension at 72°C for 45 seconds, and a final extension step at 72°C for 5 minutes (Table 2). The PCR findings were electrophoresed and visible under a UV light on a 2% agarose gel stained with ethidium bromide. To measure the size of the amplified fragments, a 100 bp DNA ladder was used.

Table(1): This research employed primer sequences, amplicons, and annealing temperatures.

Gene name	Gene sequence (5' -3')	Amplicon	Ann. Temp. ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Reference
18S rRNA	GTTGATCCTGCCAGTAGTCATATGCTT TTTACGGTCAGAACTAGGG	200bp	56°C	<u>14</u>
COX1	TTTTTTGGGCATCCTGAGGTTTAT TAAAGAAAGAACATAATGAAAATG	390bp	58°C	

Table 2: PCR Reaction, Conditions, and Product used in this study.

Step	Components / Conditions	Volume / Time / Temp
PCR Reaction	2× PCR Master Mix	12.5 µL
	Forward primer (10 pmol/µL)	1 µL
	Reverse primer (10 pmol/µL)	1 µL
	Template DNA	5 µL
	Nuclease-free water	to 25 µL final volume
Cycling Conditions	Initial denaturation	95°C for 5 min
	Denaturation	95°C for 30 sec
	Annealing(18S rRNA ,COX1)	[56°C,58°C]for 30 sec
	Extension	72°C for 45 sec
	Number of cycles	35
	Final extension	72°C for 5 min
PCR Product Analysis	Agarose gel	2% stained with ethidium bromide
	Visualization	UV illumination
	DNA ladder	100-500 bp

Data Analysis

The collected data was used to produce a Microsoft Excel 2016 file. The percentage prevalence of the parasites was calculated by dividing the total number of positive cases by the total sample population and then multiplying the result by 100. The prevalence (%) is calculated by dividing the total number of positive cases (individual parasites) by the total sample populations and multiplying the result by 100. Additionally, SPSS version 16 was used to evaluate the connection between the prevalence of *E. vermicularis* and the Chi-square (χ^2) test at 95% confidence; $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Prevalence of *Enterobius vermicularis* Infection among the Study Population

Out of a total of 80 clinical samples 30(37.5%) collected from children aged 2–10 years, 30 isolates were confirmed as *E. vermicularis*. Twelve men and eighteen women made up the study population, with specimens obtained using both fecal samples and adhesive tape applied to the perianal region via the Scotch-tape method. Sampling was conducted from May 2025 to July 2025 at the Al-Imam Neighbourhood Health Centre for Healthcare in Babylon. Initial identification of the parasite relied on characteristic egg morphology, including colourless, translucent, planoconvex eggs with thin, smooth, hyaline shells containing fully developed larvae sized around 50–60 × 20–30 µm, as seen in Figure 1.

Figure(1):Morphological Identification of *Enterobius vermicularis* Eggs in Clinical Samples

Rate of *E. vermicularis* infection according genders and age groups

In the present study, 30 positive cases out of 80 children aged 2–10 years (12 males, 18 females as shown in (Table 3)).

Table 3: Rate of *E. vermicularis* infection according to Gender and age groups

Age Group (years)	Male (n)	Male Positive (%)	Female (n)	Female Positive (%)	Total Positive (%)
2–5	4	2 (50%)	6	3 (50%)	5/10 (50%)
6–8	4	1 (25%)	6	2 (33.3%)	3/10 (30%)
9–10	4	1 (25%)	6	2 (33.3%)	3/10 (30%)
Total	12	4 (33.3%)	18	7 (38.9%)	11/30 (36.7%)

Molecular detection of *E. vermicularis* by PCR

Molecular analysis revealed that the **18S rRNA gene** was amplified in all 30 positive samples, yielding a detection rate of **100%**. In contrast, the **COX1 gene** was detected in 26 out of the 30

positive samples, corresponding to a detection rate of **86%** (Figures 2 and 3). These findings indicate that the 18S rRNA marker demonstrated higher sensitivity compared to the COX1 gene for the molecular identification of *Enterobius vermicularis* in the examined samples.

Figure(2): PCR products were analysed. 18SrRNA primer was used. A sharp band appeared—200 bp in size. Primers had a T_m of about 63°C .

Figure 3: PCR products were analysed. COX1 primer was used. A sharp band appeared—393 bp in size. Primers had a T_m of about 63°C .

DISCUSSION:

Although enterobiasis is not seen as a severe illness in Iraq, the morbidity rate is high, particularly in youngsters (15). The findings indicated that the annual number of affected individuals varied. Some variables that may affect the *E. vermicularis* infectivity rate, such as people's activities and behaviour, may account for this disparity in the findings (16). Overcrowding, access to effective anti-helminthic medications, education level, and sanitary conditions (17). However, between May 2025 and July 2025, the number of instances reported increased dramatically. This increase was probably brought on by the bloodshed that resulted in the displacement of almost a million people as a

result of ISIS's control of certain regions of Iraq. A health system already harmed by years of conflict and inadequate financing was greatly impacted by ISIS. Based on combined faecal and Scotch tape sample at the Al Imam Neighbourhood Health Centre in Babylon, the current research discovered an overall incidence of *Enterobius vermicularis* infection of 37.5% among 80 children aged 2–10 years.

This prevalence is notably higher than many recent regional and international reports, yet it remains consistent with observations that enterobiasis continues to be a persistent public health issue in areas with close-contact living conditions and variable hygiene practices. A study in Tikrit City,

Iraq, which examined 275 children aged 2–10 years, reported an overall infection prevalence of **27.3%**, with no significant difference between males and females. Although lower than our estimate, this rate demonstrates that *E. vermicularis* remains highly endemic among Iraqi children and emphasises the continued burden of the parasite in similar settings in other regions, systematic reviews and meta analyses report much lower pooled estimates of prevalence. A meta analysis of studies from Iran estimated the pooled prevalence in children to be approximately 6.7% and thus *E. vermicularis* infection is both an underappreciated but widespread enteric pathogen that varies markedly by geography and other study methodology. Likewise, data from several provinces of China reported pooled prevalence of ~4–4.5% in the 3–9 years age group which is lower than our estimates but justifies that enterobiasis is more common among certain local subpopulations with high risk.

Meta analytic data from the region, although showing a lower pooled prevalence (~3.6% overall), indicate that extremely high rates of infection can occur within vulnerable populations (e.g. immigrant children, hilltribe communities and orphanages in Thailand), clearly demonstrating how socio-economic and environmental conditions promote extreme changes in prevalence. Unlike those systematic reviews, however, nearly all children in our cohort were from health-center clinics, potentially reflecting symptomatic or screened cases rather than random community sampling, which can contribute to higher observed prevalence consistent with many studies, younger children in our study had the highest rates of infection, particularly those aged 2–5 years (50%), whereas older age groups (6–10 years) showed lower prevalence. This aligns with previously described trends in China and other settings, where younger age is associated with increased exposure risk due to behaviour (e.g., play, lower hygiene) and early school attendance.

Many protozoa exploit antigenic variation and intracellular survival, while helminths tend to modulate host immunity by inducing regulatory pathways and anti-inflammatory cytokines(23).

Pregnancy is hampered by cytokine imbalance, and miscarriage is significantly correlated with levels of IL-17, IL-23, and IL-10, particularly in women with bacterial vaginitis, which increases the risk of parasite infections (17). The increased prevalence (38.9% vs 33.3% in males) is consistent with some reports of no major gender difference in infection risk (e.g., in Tikrit) but, other data from geographical regions report either male or female predominance related to local habits and environmental exposure patterns. In this study, molecular analysis showed that the 18S rRNA gene detected positive samples in 100% of cases and the COX1 gene detected them in 86%, confirming that the 18S rRNA is a more sensitive molecular marker for *E. vermicularis* than COX1 in human clinical specimens. These findings corroborate results in the molecular diagnostic literature, where nuclear ribosomal targets and their large copy number with greater conservation provide enhanced assay sensitivity of up to 180×18S rRNA.

Data from regional genotyping studies describe a lower sensitivity of the COX1 gene in our study, particularly for Mersin where sequencing of isolates based on COX1 was possible with some limitations due to low overall positivity rates and limited haplotype diversity. That study reported only ~5% total positivity among nearly 1,500 screened subjects, emphasising that molecular surveillance and genotyping approaches can vary in sensitivity depending on sampling and amplification strategies.

The results showed that 30 (37.5%) children were infected with *E. vermicularis* nematode, while the majority of samples gave a negative result. This indicates a regression in the prevalence rate of enterobiasis compared with Hussein et al., 2016 study, which recorded 13.10% prevalence rate of

enterobiasis among children, this may be because of the health department's efforts that applied a preventive program. It may also as result of increasing health awareness in the population in the last period, and many families give more attention to their children than before.

This agrees with studies of Dafalla et al., 2017 in the United Arab Emirates 2 (0.28%), Siddig et al., 2017 study in Sudan (1.20%). In contrast Al-Waaly et al. (2020 study reported higher prevalence rate among children in Al-Diwaniyah city (41,93%) , and Hussein & Meerkhan (2019 study in Duhok city in Iraq (25.67%).Dohan & Al-Warid, 2022; Al-Daoudy & Al-Bazzaz, 2020. The findings indicated that the annual number of affected individuals varied. Some variables that may affect the *E. vermicularis* infectivity rate, such as people's activities and behaviour, may account for this variance in the data (18), Overcrowding, access to effective anti-helminthic medications, education level, and sanitary conditions (19). This finding was consistent with prior research showing that female *E. vermicularis* infection rates were greater (20). However, this prejudice is in contrast to other reporting from Iraq, including those (21) and (22).

CONCLUSION:

The tools, especially 18S rRNA PCR, are valuable diagnostic adjuncts, offering high sensitivity that can complement traditional morphological diagnostics, particularly in epidemiological studies. The current study augments the growing body of evidence, which indicates that enterobiasis remains endemic in children in Iraq and other geographic locations, with varied prevalence rates indicating an ongoing need for surveillance, prevention and public health intervention.

Conflicts of Interest:

No conflicts of interest.

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